

MADANIYAT CHORRAHALARI

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PEREKRESTOK KULTURY | CROSSROADS OF CULTURE

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PRINCIPLES OF MUSIC TEACHING

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ANNOTATION

This article provides detailed information about the influence of music on the intellectual and moral education of children, and the principles of effective organization of the learning process of students in music culture classes in secondary schools.

Key words: music, interest, principle, work, analysis, performance, lesson, fiction, process, theory.

G'oziyev Jobirxon Jo'raxonovich

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MUSIQIY O'QITISH TAMOYILLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada musiqaning bolalarning aqliy va axloqiy tarbiyasiga ta'siri, musiqa o'qituvchilarining umumta'lim maktablaridagi musiqa madaniyati darslarida o'quvchilarning dars jarayonini samarali tashkil etishdagi tamoyillar haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, qiziqish, tamoyil, asar, tahlil, ijro, dars, badiiy adabiyot, jarayon, nazariya.

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ПРИНЦИПЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ МУЗЫКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлена подробная информация о влиянии музыки на интеллектуальное и нравственное воспитание детей, а также о принципах эффективной организации учебного процесса учащихся на уроках музыкальной культуры в общеобразовательных школах.

Ключевые слова: музыка, интерес, принцип, работа, анализ, исполнение, урок, художественная литература, процесс, теория.

Introduction. Music classes are distinguished from other subjects in school by their artistic, fun and imaginative experiences. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 "On

measures to further developing the art of Uzbek national makom”, August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 “On measures for innovative development of the arts”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, is becoming increasingly important [1].

Music classes are distinguished from other subjects in school by their artistic, fun and imaginative experiences. Music has a positive effect on the mental and moral education of my child. Artistic education is its logical content. The internal structure of the music lesson consists of various examples of music history, theory and performance - vocal-choir exercises, music literacy, listening to music, music analysis and literature, playing children’s musical instruments, performing rhythmic movements. Therefore, it is a mixed class. Also, music differs from other forms of art in its means of expression, its “language”. Music is expressed by means of tones created in musical sounds, music is perceived only by listening [2. P: 12].

Music is an art associated with a definite measure of time. If you don't tune in to the rhythm of the music and listen to every element of it, you won't understand the piece perfectly. That's why when you listen to music again and again, new artistic aspects of it open up. Music lessons are organized on the basis of didactic theory and principles of pedagogy. These principles determine the main requirements and directions of the lesson content, methods and structure of the lesson.

The main laws of the teaching process are clearly expressed in the didactic principles. The principles of teaching should be understood as the primary laws that define the content, methods, and forms of organization of the educational process underlying teaching and the entire process of its implementation. There is an integral relationship between the principles. Violation of one of them automatically leads to the violation of the other. From the principles come the rules of teaching. Rules determine the nature of certain methods of the teacher and lead to the implementation of principles. Rules are developed not only by didactics, but also by specific methods relevant to the educational situation.

Principles of Consciousness and Activity. This principle is one of the leading principles of didactics. The principles of awareness and activity of students based on the leadership role of the pedagogue imply that in the process of teaching, the student has a deep understanding of the studied musical materials, understands the content and essence of the works, and as a result, is able to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in practice, because musical Knowledge acquisition depends on the knowledge process, which is the main quality of the student's mental activity. Conscious perception and knowledge of music, in turn, ensures that the work is kept stable in terms of artistic tone and logic. It is important not to forget that attention, interest and consciously learned song melody and listened music will remain in the memory for a lifetime.[3. P: 34].

Although it does not repeat itself from time to time. Methodical features of music, its polyphony, song materials, music records, not just memorizing the dates of the life of composers, but it awakens different emotions, mental experiences, imagination, aesthetic and artistic tastes in children. shoot and encourage to think about some images and ideas formed. Musical perception enriches the child's life experience, creates an artistic perception of real reality, develops cognitive abilities, and develops thinking skills. But the formation of these skills and abilities requires a long process of development in the child's mind. A child accustomed to perceive a small piece of music cannot perceive a large piece of music. So, in order for the child's ability to perceive music to reach this level, he must consciously and actively acquire the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to listen to a great piece.

But this does not happen by itself. For this purpose, it is necessary for the child to consciously master the educational materials, to create the activity of the knowledge process, using the principle of systematic and continuity in music education. A conscious attitude requires the birth of a desire to know about the content of teaching and teaching methods. A student is eager to study only when the music lesson itself is interesting. In this place, a lot depends on the teacher, his work style and method, and his attitude towards students. In order to master a certain piece of music by singing or listening to it and enjoy it artistically and aesthetically, it is necessary to be able to perceive this work, first of all, to be able to attract the child's attention and arouse interest in it. Otherwise, awareness and activity

will not arise. It is known that a person voluntarily reads, watches and perceives works of fiction, visual arts and sculptures, natural beauty and museum exhibits at a pace suitable for his artistic needs. But music is an exception to this possibility.

Because the music listener, singer, and performer must adjust to the tempo set by the composer, sing and listen at this tempo. Otherwise, there will be a disconnection between the music and the listener, and the perception will be disturbed. That is why consciousness and its activity play an important role in music lessons. Awareness and activity of the student in the lesson is necessary for the formation of vocal-choir skills. For this, it is necessary that the teacher's explanatory tools are appropriate, clear and clear, suitable for the child's vocabulary, and vocal exercises and songs are suitable for their voice and singing skills. In learning music literacy, awareness and activity facilitate the correct knowledge and mastery of music from a theoretical and practical point of view [4. P: 56].

The fact that knowledge has an active character is also shown in educational activities. Pupils can understand and master musical educational material only in the process of active cognitive activity. The student works independently due to his interest and desire to study. It happens as a result of his activeness in music lessons, his diligence, and his thirst for knowledge. In this case, the role of the music teacher is to help the student to properly organize his study time, to teach him rational methods of mental activity. Scientific, systematic and continuity principle in music lessons. the principle of humanity means the requirement that the size of the studied materials and the level of difficulty should be in accordance with the age, individual characteristics, and level of training of the participants. When implementing this principle, the teacher determines the time needed to study the musical piece, types of activities, and the question. It defines a new concept that will be understandable to students, the volume of musical expressions, the depth of coverage of the types of activities being studied, the complexity of practical performance, and teaching methods [5. P: 44].

The historical development of scientific knowledge rises from a lesser understanding to a deeper understanding of the laws of the surrounding world. Scientific knowledge can explain the world of music in different ways without losing its scientific character. That is why the musical pieces studied in the curriculum can be interpreted more or less deeply depending on the age of the students and their level of development.

For example, the National Anthem is taught in all grades. The scientific definition of this work deepens every year. Superficiality should not be allowed in the first stage of hymn teaching. Like any other lesson, music lesson should be organized on a scientific basis with its structure and content. The framework of knowledge about music is the main basis in music education and upbringing. It is reflected in the rules, conclusions, generalizations of musical experiences related to the music created by mankind. Learning they means building knowledge and skills in the way of musical practice. In the course of music lessons, the compatibility of educational materials with children's knowledge and experience, taking into account the laws of children's voice development, correctly teaching the laws of notes, analyzing works in accordance with children's perceptive abilities, etc. constitute the scientific principle of music lessons.

A scientific worldview can be formed only on the basis of a certain system of knowledge. Therefore, education should be systematic and continuous. The lesson should be the main tool, the main source of systematic formation of a person - only in such conditions it will have great educational value. The ability to provide systematic knowledge can be inculcated in students only if the music lesson follows the principles of structure and continuity of education in its work. Science cannot be done without systematicity. All types of activities of the music lesson and the logical connection of the subsequent lessons form a system. The same piece of music can be studied in different ways, methods, and tools. The teacher can find the most suitable system of teaching the work for the specific situation. Systematic selection of works for singing and listening according to the level of children's knowledge and skills, vocal and choral skills, as well as the principle of mastery from simple to complex and from the known to the unknown [6. P: 32].

Each element of the lesson, in turn, is a logical continuation of the previous lesson, and the continued implementation of pedagogical goals means the principle of continuity. During musical activities, the student's ability to study, diligence or laziness, reluctance to study, determination or

laziness, self-discipline or interest or lack of interest in learning, little or quick fatigue and similar characteristics are manifested. The system of educational work, if the teacher plans the system of influence in advance, helps to cultivate positive qualities in the child in each lesson. The principle of demonstration in music lessons. The essence of the principle of demonstrability is that the teacher creates a clear, clear idea for the students about the studied music science and its activities. Such imaginations are the basis for a deeper understanding of the musical work. It is worth noting that visualization does not only play the role of a source of knowledge, but also affects the development of students. The use of visualization helps the development of thinking and speech, facilitates the transition from abstract to concrete, helps to organize perception and attention.

The principle of demonstrability is implemented under the following conditions:

- demonstrability corresponds to the purpose and task of the lesson;
- demonstration is carried out in addition to verbal explanation;
- demonstration is not used excessively in the lesson;
- the teacher correctly determines the place, time and duration of the demonstration;
- is based on the characteristics and level of preparation of students in the implementation of

demonstration. In music education, music itself is a demonstration tool.

Because it is not perceived by the eyes, but by the ears. For example, when the teacher plays and sings the melody of a song or exercise, the melody and the words are mainly perceived by the ear. Both in listening to music and in the analysis of the work, the melody is played as an exhibition. With the help of words, the teacher leads the students to understand and express the connections that cannot be "seen" in the process of perception of the work based on their observations of the visual object and their existing knowledge. Students get the main information from the teacher's verbal explanation, while the visual aids either confirm or clarify the information. Visual aids are a means of creating new emotional images in the student's mind and recalling existing ones.

Many objects, phenomena, visual teaching aids and tools that exist in the surrounding world for music science are not included. What exists in nature becomes a visual tool if, firstly, it is separated from the real conditions of its existence (a leaf is cut off and a herbarium is taken, a bird is caged), and secondly, it is used in the educational process. In a music lesson, the teacher's hand movements while playing, facial expression and facial expressions while singing, conducting, song poster hanging on the blackboard, graphic lines expressing the pitch and pitch, handouts, exercise notes are also visual aids, but it is the sound of music. It can be proved by the fact that even a blind person can perceive music, but he cannot perceive fine art, he cannot see the beauty of nature. He can visualize them in musical tones. In the course of lessons, the use of color pictures suitable for the content of the work helps to clearly imagine and perceive the artistic content of the work.

Playing musical sounds through the keyboard is especially important in the formation of early cognitive skills. The comprehensive use of the principle of demonstration of teaching requires the guidance and control of all aspects of students' emotional knowledge. The principle of comprehensive development and consistency of students' cognitive abilities in the lesson. One of the tasks of teaching is that students acquire solid knowledge, skills and competences that they can always apply in practice. The principles of sustainability imply the need to arm the student with knowledge, skills and abilities that are quickly and clearly remembered, long-retained in memory, and skillfully applied in practice. The music lesson should not only provide knowledge, but also ensure that students master the fundamentals of science. The teacher needs to know the special methods and tools that ensure this stability [7. P: 65].

For example, several types of repetition are used for the formation of musical perception, artistic performance of a song, and ensuring the solidity of the acquisition of knowledge gained from music literacy, as well as for the musical development of students. Current repetition or initial reinforcement is when your students recall the music they just heard. This type of repetition is carried out immediately after the teacher's discussion about the music listened to, in order to prevent the loss of ideas and concepts that have been created. Generalizing repetition allows for a wider level of generalizations to be applied. After the entire topic is covered, general conclusions are made, connections between types of musical activity are established, knowledge is systematized.

Figurative repetition allows you to highlight the main idea that should be captured. At the end of the quarter, a single theme can be used to cover even several songs with figurative repetition. The use of the mentioned types of repetition should ensure the stability of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students. Repetition should be systematic and timely. It is necessary to bring diversity to the process of repetition, to focus on musical activities, to eliminate ambiguities and errors, to deepen existing knowledge and the connection of knowledge with relevant skills and competencies.

Listening to music and singing a song over and over again is an effective tool. It should be noted that all the principles of teaching are closely and integrally connected with each other. Demonstration helps conscious and active acquisition of knowledge. Musical works that are reworked in the mind, conscious in singing and correctly expressed are firmly mastered. Works that are understandable to students, that is, works that are suitable for their age and individual characteristics and level of preparation, can be mastered consciously. Systematized knowledge is absorbed more thoroughly. The stability of mastering educational topics depends on many factors: scientific and systematic teaching, awareness of understanding, cognitive activity of students, reasons for studying, quality of music textbooks, skill of the music teacher.

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